

Teleoperation and Semi-Autonomy System for Research on Robotic tasks in Nuclear Glovebox Environments

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Abstract—Research and development around the deployment of robots inside constrained environments like gloveboxes is of growing interest due to the benefits of working in enclosed and difficult to access spaces. As the move from script-based programming, going to teleoperation and higher degrees of automation and autonomy is currently being pursued, a flexible system architecture allowing to seamlessly change between modes of operation is required. Such a system needs to deal with different robotic platforms and software packages, some running legacy operating systems not upgradable due to internal business policies. We present a platform to simultaneously perform teleoperation and task automation, integrating sensor perception and machine learning loops for legacy and new-build gloveboxes. The system has been deployed and tested with different robotic platforms, various haptic-capable input devices, perception tools, and performing different nuclear decommissioning tasks. The system is being used for research and development of new robotic solutions based on Robotic Operating System (ROS)1 and ROS2. Here we share our application requirements, system design and the tools used to develop it.

Index Terms—Telerobotics and Teleoperation, Robotics in Hazardous Fields, Reactive and Sensor-Based Planning, Control Architectures and Programming, Software, Middleware and Programming Environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

The quick adoption of robotics in different sectors opens is being driven by different commercial and technological factors. Reduction in costs and increased availability of Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) robotic systems, together with improvements in sensing, control, planning, and machine learning technologies are enablers to discuss the possibility of deploying robots performing either autonomously or semi-autonomously. A sector which could be benefited from such advances is the nuclear energy sector, particularly nuclear decommissioning, as dealing with dangerous substances during prolonged periods of time are not desirable for human operators.

The second half of the 2020s marks a transition period towards creating constant deployment pipelines with robotic systems, for which flexible and scalable systems are required. Such systems need to integrate different functionalities and modes of operation for easy and seamless mode switching, for both experimentation and operations.

Such systems are growing in demand for both research and commercial settings, with bespoke integrations following each

project's needs. However, systems for either manual/offline programming or teleoperation tend to be designed and executed separately. For manual/offline programming, users rely on either scripting languages provided by the robot suppliers (e.g., URScript for Universal Robots, Kinova Kortex WebApp creating, Doosan TaskWriter), on commercial offerings like RoboDK [1], or on systems based on middleware like ROS1/ROS2 like MoveIt [2]. For teleoperation, users either rely on supplier's functionality to jog at cartesian or joint level (i.e., control velocity) or custom solutions like the Haption [3], [4] and TREX box, or recent offerings from suppliers like the UR AI Accelerator [5]. Most modern robotic suppliers provide a networked mechanism to interact with their products. This is often an Ethernet, TCP/IP-like interface, exchanging datagrams between the robot's internal control computer and an external client (e.g., computer or Programmable Logic Controller (PLC)). This is done in a synchronous or asynchronous way, depending on the available control modes (e.g., Universal Robots Real-Time Data Exchange (RTDE)) and network frequency rates. Such functionality is the basis of most software offerings, using the official low-level programming libraries offered by the supplier or a re-implementations of such protocols [6].

In order to explore semi-autonomous behaviour and ways to share control between human input and programmed or automated robot control, both offline programming and teleoperation functionalities are needed. Standardization frameworks acting as middleware like ROS1/ROS2 provide a good basis for message serialization and forms of Inter Process Communication (IPC), aimed at popular Operating System (OS) for development like Ubuntu Long-term Support (LTS). Such middleware can be of great help when designing a robotic system, but ROS1's End of Life (EoL) and the constant challenges around supporting legacy software and hardware components in an IT department are challenging. In addition, robotic deployments for nuclear decommissioning are still not standardized for one particular robotic manipulator (e.g., Kinova Gen3, Universal Robots UR10e), teleoperation device (e.g., Haption, Haply) or glovebox environment (e.g., legacy and new-builds).

We introduce a software and hardware platform, deployed in both legacy and new-build gloveboxes, aimed at testing, prototyping and exploration of autonomy and shared control for nuclear decommissioning tasks as seen in Figure 1. This platform has been used to explore different applications before testing as non-active and active demonstrators, using both the Kinova Gen3 and UR10e robotic platforms. The remaining of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the design

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Fig. 1. High-level system description.

requirements around semi-autonomy exploration of robotic tasks, and Section III explains our resulting system design and its relevant components. Finally, Section IV discusses conclusions and future work.

II. DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

Requirements for this system considered functionality, flexibility of use and maintainability during project timelines.

Functionality was around enabling modes of operation (i.e., teleoperation, automation, semi-autonomy), with seamless switching between modes. Similar task functionality should be replicated in different system without large reconfigurations or programming. Maintainability of this system included how to safely maintain an application and ensuring it can be used after a project's timeline (i.e., 1 to 2 years).

This list was used for specific aspects considered:

- **Support for multi-robot platform:** Work on both legacy (i.e., designed for human operations) and new-build gloveboxes (i.e., designed for robotic operations). Legacy glovebox applications are being deployed around the Kinova Gen3 7 degrees of freedom (DoF) robots, and new-build applications around the Universal Robots UR10e robot, as seen in Figure 3. Other robots like the Unitree Z1 and meca500 are used for demonstration purposes.
- **Support for multiple input devices:** Restrictions regarding deployment space and work with different industries forced the system to be compatible with more than one input device to guide the robot's end effector in position and orientation during teleoperation. Haptics-capable devices were preferred.
- **Support for integrating sensing, planning and machine-learning capabilities:** Applications need integration of RGB and RGBD cameras with computer vision and machine learning algorithms, for either in eye-in-hand and eye-on-base configurations [7]. This includes detection of objects of interest for obstacle evasion, object retrieval and plane detection.
- **Support for legacy software/hardware:** Considering tight IT policies for institutions, there is a need to support

software components under OS which could stop its LTS support, for at least the remaining of a project (e.g., Ubuntu 20 and ROS1). In the same way, this system needs to run on newer OS when new computing devices are added.

- **Flexibility to expand to different tasks:** The system should be able to accommodate more tasks involving free motion, handling of tools or potentially high-level planning tools for structured decision-making.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN

A system enabling teleoperation, task automation and semi-autonomous behaviours was designed. A high-level architecture of its different hardware/software components can be seen as an Appendix, Figure 2. The system is designed to run on modern Linux OS above Ubuntu 20, it can run on desktop or laptop computers with Ethernet 1 Gbps and USB 3.0 based on the robotic system controlled. It takes advantage of Docker for container management for both machine vision and machine learning processes, as well as to enable legacy software running software only compatible with the latest OS. It uses ROS topics and parameters where possible to serialize and exchange messages between relevant processes.

The most relevant aspects of the system are as follows:

- Low-level controllers to interact with each robot were written in C++, using the functionality provided by each robotic supplier. This sets the robot's initial configuration, reads joint information and performs joint-level control (i.e., position-based where servoing is possible, or velocity-based with a Proportional Differential (PD) controller from position input, as seen in Equation 1). Control frequency was set around or lower than 100 Hz, as to reduce the impact of burst delays due to other workloads in the system (e.g, machine learning).
- relaxedIK and collisionIK [8] were used as inverse kinematic solvers and collision avoidance handlers. This was implemented in a continuous optimization loop, with a custom update algorithm used at the low-level code, as seen in Algorithm 1.

- Modes of operation were implemented as states with state transitions based on user input, as seen in Figure 4. User input was mapped to the robot's end effector frame inside the glovebox environment during each mode change to enable seamless transition, as seen in Algorithm 2.
- Exact polynomial splines in translation and rotation are used for automatic motion and haptic guidance trajectories. Splines are generated using the `ndcurves` [9] library.
- A state indicator using LED colours was created using `micro-ros` [10] and a `rp2040` Microcontroller Unit (MCU).
- Container-based Machine-learning and Machine vision functionality was implemented using `Docker-nvidia` to enable access to the GPU. Functionality explored includes:
 - Object detection using `YOLO` [11].
 - Object segmentation using `Unseen Object` [12].
 - Grasp pose generation using `Graspnet` [13].
 - Fiducial markers tracking with `ARUCO` markers [14].
- Container-based functionality using `Docker` and `Robot-Stack` [15] to make legacy OS work with `ROS1` build system:
 - The `ROS1` interface for the `haply` [16] device was done using `RobotStack` and built on an `Ubuntu 24` container, to then run on any `Linux` host.
- 3D-printed attachments were used for mounting cameras on robotic grippers for eye-in-hand operation (Figure 5, and as gripping blocks on tools to ease grasping.

This system was tested and used for the Legacy glovebox environment with a `Kinova Gen3 7 DoF`, and for new-build applications around the `Universal Robots UR10e` robot. The use cases explored include object grasping and handling (e.g., retrieving objects from an entryport), tool handling (e.g., radiation surveying using `DP6` radiation probe) and object reconstruction.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

We designed a system to explore the use inside legacy and new-build gloveboxes, under different robotic systems for an initial set of tasks. The system is capable of extending both teleoperation and automated programming capabilities, and helps to explore ways to perform shared control, achieving semi-autonomy. A manual-switch, shared control strategy was created, that enables further automatic switching modes.

Future work will focus on including formalism to describe robotic tasks [17] from the nuclear decommissioning context, and integration with industrial digital twins with standard connectors (`ros2` connectors, `Open Platform Communications (OPC) Unified Architecture (UA)` [18]).

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Kumar, S. Anand, P. S. Bharti, M. K. Satyarthi, P. Kumar, and A. Kumar, *Progressive Automation: Mapping the Horizon of Smart Manufacturing with RoboDK Workstations and Industry 4.0*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2024, pp. 335–354. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-68271-1_15
- [2] M. Görner, R. Haschke, H. Ritter, and J. Zhang, “Moveit! task constructor for task-level motion planning,” in *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 190–196.

- [3] P. Garrec, J.-P. Friconneau, and F. Louveau, “Virtuose 6d: A new force-control master arm using innovative ball-screw actuators,” in *Proceedings of OSR2004–35th Symposium on Robotics, Paris, France march*, 2004.
- [4] E. J. L. Pulgarin, O. Tokatli, G. Burroughes, and G. Herrmann, “Assessing tele-manipulation systems using task performance for glovebox operations,” *Frontiers in Robotics and AI*, vol. 9, p. 323, 11 2022.
- [5] U. Robots, “Ai accelerator,” <https://www.universal-robots.com/products/ai-accelerator/>, accessed: 2025-04-02.
- [6] A. P. Lindvig, I. Iturrate, U. Kindler, and C. Sloth, “ur_rtdc: An interface for controlling universal robots (ur) using the real-time data exchange (rtdc),” in *2025 IEEE/SICE International Symposium on System Integration (SII)*, 2025, pp. 1118–1123.
- [7] R. Y. Tsai, R. K. Lenz *et al.*, “A new technique for fully autonomous and efficient 3 d robotics hand/eye calibration,” *IEEE Transactions on robotics and automation*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 345–358, 1989.
- [8] D. Rakita, H. Shi, B. Mutlu, and M. Gleicher, “Collisionik: A per-instant pose optimization method for generating robot motions with environment collision avoidance,” in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 9995–10001.
- [9] S. Tonneau, J. Chemin, P. Fernbach, and G. Saurel, “ndcurves,” 2013. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/loco-3d/ndcurves>
- [10] K. Belsare, A. C. Rodriguez, P. G. Sánchez, J. Hierro, T. Kolcon, R. Lange, I. Lütkebohle, A. Malki, J. M. Losa, F. Melendez, M. M. Rodriguez, A. Nordmann, J. Staschulat, and J. von Mendel, *Micro-ROS*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2023, pp. 3–55. [Online]. Available: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-09062-2_2
- [11] G. Jocher, J. Qiu, and A. Chaurasia, “Ultralytics YOLO,” Jan. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>
- [12] Y. Xiang, C. Xie, A. Mousavian, and D. Fox, “Learning rgb-d feature embeddings for unseen object instance segmentation,” in *Conference on Robot Learning (CoRL)*, 2020.
- [13] M. Sundermeyer, A. Mousavian, R. Triebel, and D. Fox, “Contact-graspnet: Efficient 6-dof grasp generation in cluttered scenes,” 2021.
- [14] M. Kalaitzakis, B. Cain, S. Carroll, A. Ambrosi, C. Whitehead, and N. Vitzilaios, “Fiducial markers for pose estimation: Overview, applications and experimental comparison of the artag, apriltag, aruco and stag markers,” *Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems*, vol. 101, pp. 1–26, 2021.
- [15] T. Fischer, W. Vollprecht, S. Traversaro, S. Yen, C. Herrero, and M. Milford, “A rostack tutorial: Using the robot operating system alongside the conda and jupyter data science ecosystems,” *IEEE Robotics and Automation Magazine*, 2021.
- [16] R. Haply, “Haply, bringing touch to technology,” <https://www.haply.co/>, 2024, accessed: 2025-03-27.
- [17] “Ieee standard for robot task representation,” *IEEE Std 1872.1-2024*, pp. 1–32, 2024.
- [18] T. Hannelius, M. Salmenpera, and S. Kuikka, “Roadmap to adopting opc ua,” in *2008 6th IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics*, 2008, pp. 756–761.

SYSTEM DIAGRAMS AND STATE TRANSITIONS

Figure 2 describes how different software and hardware components are used and integrated to create this system. External inputs are used together with user input to control the robotic system and the states transition.

Fig. 2. High-level system architecture of components and its interaction.

Figure 3 shows robotic systems for both legacy gloveboxes and new-build gloveboxes. Legacy gloveboxes are designed to be used by human operators for manual operation, and require an additional mechanism to put a robotic system inside. New-build gloveboxes are designed around a robotic system.

(a) Robotic system for Legacy glovebox

(b) Robotic system for new-build glovebox

Fig. 3. Gloveboxes environments used for robotic systems.

Figure 4 shows how the states transition works, based on the user input. After the system is initialized, it goes to an idle state, from where any other state can be reached based on the user inputs. All modes can be stopped with the user input.

Fig. 4. State transitions to manage different modes of operation.

Figure 5 shows different attachments for the Realsense D435i camera on three robotic grippers.

Fig. 5. 3D-printed attachments for different grippers.

MOTION EQUATIONS

Equation 1 shows the continuous control loop equations of a PD controller. This was used when there was no servoing functionality in the robot (i.e., a goal joint position is continuously being requested). This was used in the Kinova Gen3 robot.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q}_d &= q_\epsilon k_P + ((q_\epsilon - q_{\epsilon-1}) \Delta t) k_D \\ q_\epsilon &= q_d - q \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

\dot{q}_d as desired joint velocity, q_ϵ as joint position error, q_d as desired joint position, q as current joint position, k_P as proportional constant and k_D as derivative constant.

Algorithm 1 manages the inverse kinematic solver's output to use new solutions that changed a certain delta. This works as a low-pass filter.

Algorithm 1 Threshold to process new inverse kinematic solution

Require: ikSolution

```

1: if ikInitialized = false then
2:   ikPrevSolution ← ikSolution
3:   ikInitialized ← true
4: end if
5: ikDifferences ← ikPrevSolution – ikSolution
6: if ikDifferences > ikThreshold then
7:   ikPrevSolution ← ikSolution
8:    $q_d \leftarrow$  ikSolution
9: else
10:   $q_d \leftarrow$  ikPrevSolution
11: end if

```

Algorithm 2 manages mapping the relative position and orientation between the user's input device and the controlled robot. This is done after initialization and after each state transition.

Algorithm 2 Mapping reference frames for mode switching

Require: inputPosition, inputRotation, systemStarted, motionSource

```

1: if systemStarted = false and motionSource = userInput then
2:   if poseInitialized = false then
3:     TOROTFRAME(inputPosition,inputRotation)
4:     initialPosition ← inputPositionInRobot + positionInRobot
5:     initialRotation ← inputRotationInRobot
6:     initialRotationHRID ← rotationInRobot
7:     poseInitialized ← true
8:   end if
9:   TOROTFRAME(inputPosition,inputRotation)
10:  positionInRobot ← initialPosition – inputPositionInRobot
11:  rotationInRobot ← initialRotationHRID ⊗ inputRotationInRobot ⊗ initialRotation))
12: end if
13: function TOROTFRAME(position,rotation)
14:    $\mathbf{T}(\text{positionInRobot}, \text{rotationInRobot}) \leftarrow \mathbf{T}(\text{position}, \text{rotation})^{\text{user}}\mathbf{H}_{\text{robot}}$ 
15: end function

```

⊗ as quaternion multiplication and \hat{q} as quaternion conjugate. $\mathbf{T}(\text{position}, \text{rotation})$ as position and orientation in homogeneous transformation matrix form, and ${}^{\text{user}}\mathbf{H}_{\text{robot}}$ as homogeneous transformation matrix mapping user coordinate frame to robot coordinate frame.
